

Module 1: The basic principles of photonics

Chapter 1: Exploring and controlling the light

Why can we see objects?

In Ancient Greece, we used to say that the light came from the eyes to identify objects as seen in cartoons.

This statement is false. Indeed, we can see objects because they reflect a portion of the light that is received. We cannot see an object that receives no light as it will be unable to reflect a light to our eyes. This is the case of an object in the dark.

In contrast, we can see certain objects because they emit light. This is the case of the sun, stars, lights, candles and flames: it's what we call primary sources of lights.

What is light?

In 1666, during his optical experiments, Newton passes the white sunlight through a prism. He notices that the output of the prism, that white light, is divided into several different colour lights. These are the rainbow colours.

Newton understands with this experience that the white light is separated into its components because each colour beam is deflected differently by the glass of the prism. Thus, he notices for example that the red light is always less deviated than purple one.

Newton therefore understands that when white light passes from one transparent medium (such as air) to another (such as glass), its components are deflected a first time by colour and when they emerge in air, they are again deflected, creating a luminous rays spread from red to purple, like the colours of the rainbow.

Why can we see a rainbow in the sky after the rain?

When the sun illuminates a thin mist (e.g. near water falls) or the charged atmosphere of thin droplets, you can see a rainbow. In reality, the droplets act as mini-prisms. White light enters inside the round droplet, reflects and springs. It is "decomposed."

How does the light react when it runs into an object?

When incident light enters into the interface between two environment such as air and water, we see two things:

- A small portion of the light is reflected: this is the partial reflection phenomenon.
- A major portion of the beam enters in the water with a change of direction; the beam appears decomposed. This phenomenon whereby light changes direction when it passes from one transparent medium to another is called refraction.

Moreover, there are two types of reflection:

- The first type is: specular reflection. This reflection appears when the radiation reflected by the surface occurs in a single direction. This is done only on smooth surfaces such as mirrors.

The rays are reflected in a direction related to the angle at which they hit the object, much like a billiard ball hitting on a bar.

The second type is diffuse reflection. When the surfaces are rough with asperities, the reflection is diffuse. The radiation is reflected in all directions because of the heterogeneity of the environment, usually with a preferred direction where you can observe more reflection.

Why an object that is illuminated by white light takes a particular colour?

The colour of objects around us depends on the light they diffuse.

To summarize, in the diffusion phenomenon, an object receives light and returns a small part in all directions.

When diffusing a portion of the received white light is absorbed, the other is returned and gives colour to the object: a red object absorbs all the colours of white light except the red, green object absorbs all the lights except the green, etc.

Thus, an object which is illuminated by a white light has the colour of light it does not absorb.

How does a white subject react when illuminated by white light?

By illuminating a white surface, almost all the light rays of white light are reflected.

How does a black subject react when illuminated by a white light?

By illuminating a black surface, there is substantially no reflected light because the surface will absorb the radiation. The absence of light at the observer's eye level is translated by the brain as a black colour.

How does a colour object react when illuminated by white light?

By illuminating a blue surface (or other), the material absorbs the other colours and transforms them into heat. Only scattered blue light can reach the observer's eye. This object then seems blue.

Quiz for chapter 1:

1. We are able to see because:

- a. Our eyes emit light
- b. Objects emit light
- c. Objects reflect light

2. An object is green because it:

- a. Absorbs green light
- b. Reflects green light
- c. Transmits green light

3. An object that absorbs all light is:

- a. Invisible
- b. Black
- c. White

Chapter 2: Light behaves both as a particle and as a wave

What is light?

Light is a form of energy like electricity. It is composed of tiny particles of light called "photons" moving in the form of an electromagnetic wave.

What is the light made of?

White light is composed of coloured lights: the primary colours such as blue, green and red as the secondary colours such as yellow, cyan and magenta. The colours diffuse along different waves (one per colour).

What is a wave?

A wave is the propagation of a disturbance, which produces on its way a reversible change in physical properties of the local environment. It moves with a given speed which depends on the characteristics of environment. A wave carries energy without transporting matter.

The light, which is an electromagnetic wave, can be easily spread in the space (vacuum). In vacuum and in the air, the light waves are propagated at a speed of 300 000km / s.

What is the electromagnetic spectrum?

The electromagnetic spectrum includes the set of all the electromagnetic waves according to their wavelength and frequency.

Located between the infrared and ultraviolet, visible spectrum occupies only a small place in the full electromagnetic spectrum. Other animals or insects do not have the same vision as us: their visibility spectrum can be shifted into the IR (mosquitoes) or UV (bees).

How light rays are born?

Everything around us is made of infinitely small particles: the atoms.

An atom consists of a nucleus around which electrons rotate. Atom is often represented like our solar system, the sun (nucleus) is surrounded by planets (electrons).

We can imagine that inside an atom, the electrons rotate around the nucleus in circular orbits. The electrons that revolve on a close orbit near the nucleus have lower energy than those who revolve on a more distant orbit.

Inside an atom, an electron orbit may change under certain conditions. For example, an electron can move from a high orbit to a low orbit. It moves from a state where it has a lot of energy towards a state where it has fewer (the electron releases the energy). This amount of energy released, which must be somewhere (in physics, nothing "disappears"), takes the form of an "energy package", called "photon".

A light source generates this large-scale phenomenon of photon generation.

Quiz for chapter 2:

1. What characterizes the model of light?
 - a. Light is a particle.
 - b. Light is a wave.
 - c. Light is a wave and a particle.

2. What are the characteristics of white light?
 - a. It contains the primary and secondary colours that make up the visible range
 - b. It contains only the primary colours that do not make up for the entire visible range
 - c. It contains the primary and secondary colours that do not make up the visible range

3. What happens when an atom goes from higher state $n = 2$ to ground state $n = 1$?
 - a. The atom has the highest energy and a photon is absorbed
 - b. The atom has a lower energy and a photon is emitted.
 - c. The atom does not change and a photon is emitted.

Chapter 3: Mirrors and lenses

What is a lens?

The lenses are made from a transparent material (glass or plastic). It can be observed that all these lenses are delimited by two smooth surfaces of which at least one is a curved surface. They are all symmetrical with respect to an axis called the optical axis.

The lenses can be classified into two types:

- Those whose centre is thicker than the edges are converging lenses (top line on the previous drawing).

- Those whose edges are wider than the centre are divergent lenses (bottom line on the previous drawing).

In optics, a focus is a point where the light rays emitted from a source converge after passing through an optical system (eg.lens).

What is a converging lens?

By illuminating a converging lens with a parallel light beam, we can focus the light into a small spot almost reduced to a point. If we place a piece of paper at this point, it ignites. This is what we call the focus of lens.

What is a diverging lens?

By illuminating a diverging lens with a parallel beam of light, we can see that the light beam is deflected when it passes through the lens.

How an image is formed with a lens?

When an illuminated object is at a distance from the lens greater than the focal length f , the lens forms its image inverted, at a distance; this image can be observed on a screen.

What is a mirror?

Quiz for chapter 3:

1- What is a converging lens?

- a. A transparent object with thinner edges than the centre
- b. An opaque object with thicker edges than the centre
- c. An opaque object with thinner edges than the centre

2- What is the focal length?

- a. The distance between the focus and the lens
- b. The distance between the optical centre and the lens
- c. The distance between the optical centre and the focus

3- The image given by a mirror on a screen is?

- a. The same
- b. Reverse

Chapter 4: The concept of the laser

What is an excited atom?

It is said that an atom is in its ground state if electrons are located on lower orbits (the closest to the nucleus). In this case the atom is in its idle state and has the lowest possible energy.

In an atom, in the ground state, if an electron escapes the attraction of the nucleus and goes to a higher orbit, then we say that the atom is in an excited state. It has a higher energy than the ground state.

What is the spontaneous emission?

An excited atom can spontaneously lose his excitement when the electron moves from a high orbit to a lower orbit via a high orbit to a low orbit. In this case it loses energy by emitting a photon.

What is absorption?

In an atom, an electron can also move from a low orbit to a higher orbit if given enough energy.

What is stimulated emission?

If an atom that is already in an excited state (electron on an upper orbit) receives a photon, the electron "pushed" by the incident photon releases a second photon exactly equal to the first and falls in its lower energy state. The excited atom plays the role of "photons photocopier." For a photon received it releases 2.

What is the laser effect?

Now imagine that we use the two identical photons from the stimulated emission (see above) to interact with other two excited other atoms, then we get four photons in the same condition and so on by cascade effect: it is the laser effect.

Readily be understood that in the laser effect, there has been amplification of light intensity and all the photons are in the same state, it is called coherent light. The feature of this laser is coherent light where photons are all in the same state (direction, frequency, polarization, phase). Since the frequency of the light wave corresponds to a colour (in the visible spectrum), a highly directional beam of a very pure single colour is obtained. The colour in question depends on the basic atom which was used as the emitted light frequency depends on the distance between the two energy levels between which the electrons 'jump'.

How do you make a laser?

The laser effect is based on the stimulated emission. Imagine a material, the amplifying medium, where the atoms are mostly in an excited state. Sooner or later, an atom will emit a photon by spontaneous emission, and this photon will induce a cascade stimulated emission: the laser beam is born.

To ensure an emission in the selected direction, and increase the effect of the stimulated emission, the amplifying medium is placed between two mirrors so that the light makes many return before being transmitted: thanks to this cavity optical amplification gains in efficiency.

What are the different applications of the laser?

Laser applications are numerous. The laser has replaced many processes by improving them while being less invasive. Here is a non-exhaustive list:

The laser in medicine

The laser beam can indeed be so thin that it reaches only one cell. Therefore, it can be used in several applications in medicine.

Laser in Ophthalmology

One of the best known applications of laser in medicine is the treatment of myopia. Fast (five to ten minutes), painless, and ultimately the operation laser eye became an act common for doctors and almost miraculous solution for patients.

Laser in dermatology

The laser is very useful in dermatology for the treatment of haemangioma, rosacea, age spots and scars.

Laser in dental surgery

The dental laser is now essential in the medical world. It presents real advantages over traditional techniques. The laser offers many advantages in dental surgery: precision, safety, absence of bleeding and postoperative pain, better healing.

Laser in industry

In industry, lasers are used for their power and precision in tagging operations, welding, drilling or blasting. Unlike conventional tools, they have the advantage not to wear out.

Laser in cutting

Laser cutting is a manufacturing process that uses a laser to cut the material (metal, wood) due to the large amount of energy concentrated on a very small surface.

Laser in drilling

Accurate and fast, laser drilling allows obtaining small holes of varying geometries, for applications as glass on metal or plastic.

Laser in engraving and marking

A laser beam which energy is concentrated on a very small surface destroys the material by burning. It is the cavity obtained by removing the material that creates the engraving. Even with low-power lasers, a beam focus on a very small area allows local destruction by vaporization. This marking method is very accurate, it allows the engraving of photos or complex designs on all types of materials.

Laser in arming

Missile (airborne or ground-based)

Laser designator: laser light source for guiding a projectile (missile) or facilitating the targeting by means of a laser pointing on light arms.

Laser in the information technologies

Optical fiber

The optical fibers are made of a transparent material, glass or plastic, and have the ability to conduct light in the manner of a pipe conducting the water. The same light comes out of an optical fiber that has been put into it. Optical fiber refers to a technique and a technology for transmitting information over computer networks. The optical fiber is spreading as an Internet access because it allows very high-speed downloads.

CD / CD ROM

The readout of the CD is done using an infrared laser spot.

Quiz for chapter 4:

- 1- What is the necessary requirement to create a laser?
 - a. spontaneous emission
 - b. Absorption
 - c. stimulated emission
- 2- How does light spreads from a laser?
 - a. Parallel and straight
 - b. Perpendicular to the source
- 3- What is the laser effect?
 - a. Merging of multiple laser beams
 - b. Stimulated emission cascade

Module 2: Photonics for ICT

Optical communications

High-speed Internet is now present in every city. This technology has developed rapidly thanks to the optical fiber. Why this method is used worldwide? How can we all have access to these services in our homes?

What is fiber optics?

When you using internet or even watch TV, all information that you receive first requires many cables before arriving in your home. Current cables allow us to have a "low speed network" compared to a new cable system technology: fiber optics.

The optical fiber is a glass network. It is a cylinder composed of a heart of silica (core), a sheath (cladding) and a protective layer. Transmission of digital information takes place inside the core with the propagation of the light that obeys the laws of refraction. Thus, the beam is reflected along the optical fiber.

The transmission of information is carried by light, it takes place inside the **core** of the fiber. With the propagation of light, obeying the laws of refraction, this information moves very fast. Thus, the beam is reflected along the optical fiber.

How Optical Fiber Works?

Among other types of data transmission such as radio waves, electrical systems or Wi-Fi, it is possible to use the light to ensure **fast communications**.

For this kind of transmission, the **Optical fiber** is used: it consists in a thin glass fiber (its diameter is not higher as some micrometers) which enables the light to travel with a good celerity. The fiber is often not uniform concerning the optical index: either it has a core of higher index and an outer layer of slightly lower index, or the indices describe a gradient from the core to the outside of the fiber.

Thanks to the Law of refraction between the glass fiber and the air, the **light remains trapped in the fiber** and is able to run through kilometers of it. The optical transmission is faster than copper- based electrical transmission because it is not vulnerable to electro-magnetical fields, which can be caused by lifts, underground transportation...

There is however a loss induced by the length of the fiber, which is quantified in decibels per kilometer (dB/km). This loss depends on the material used while crafting the fiber; losses are nowadays more than ten times lower than in the 70's when the first optical fibers were developed. Those first fibers were, as an example, used by the NASA for the cameras sent to the Moon with the Apollo program.

Optical transmitter & receiver

"Transmission" is the action to send information from a point A (emission) to a point B (reception). For example, when you access to a web page, the information goes a server (point A) to your internet box (point B) by cables.

In order to transmit data through optical fibers it is also necessary to use two other devices: one to emit the light and another to receive it.

The **emitting function** is usually realized either with a **Light-Emitting Diode** (LED), which provides a signal sufficient for low-range applications, in a wide range of wavelengths (visible or infra-red) or with a **laser** (or laser diode), which is mostly used for long-range transmission, and only rarely in the visible spectrum: the most common wavelengths are situated in the infrared (IR) spectrum (1310 or 1550 nm).

At the other end of the fiber, the **signal is received** through a **photodiode** (or phototransistor). This device converts the incident photons into electrons, which then form an electrical current proportional to the photonic one.

The conceiver of the whole system must choose the photodiode according to the wavelength used for the transmission, since photodiodes are suited for precise ranges of the spectrum.

What is WDM?

The optical fiber allows us to transmit information very quickly. However, the throughput can be improved with the WDM (wavelength division multiplexing).

Indeed, instead of sending one signal using one wavelength in the optical fiber, this technique transmits multiple digital signals but with different wavelengths. It therefore necessary to have several transmitters of different wavelengths of radiation. These beams are multiplexed and then injected into the optical fiber. At the exit, they must be separated due to different radiuses and demultiplexed according to wavelength.

Quiz for chapter 1

- 1- What do we find in the core of optical fiber?
 - a) A wave
 - b) A light ray
 - c) electricity

- 2- What is broadband?
 - a) Flow rate of 100 Mbits / second
 - b) rate of 1 Gbit / sec
 - c) Throughput 10 Gbits / sec

- 3- The optical fiber enables to:
 - a) Transmit data faster than electrical transmission.
 - b) Transmit light across the seas.
 - c) Transmit light inside a human body.

Optical storage

CDs and DVDs are everywhere, but how can a movie or music be stored in an optical disc? Why do DVDs have larger capacity than CDs, even if they are both the same size?

What is a CD?

Light and its properties are also used in optical storage, and lead to technologies involved in the CD, DVD, Blu-ray, or physical supports for video games.

The CD was invented in 1982 by Sony and Philips. It appears as a disc of 12 cm in diameter and 1.2 mm in thickness and is used for storing digital information; music, movie or pictures. Its composition of four layers is quite simple:

- A printed side where the film's title is registered
- A protective film to protect data
- A reflective film where the data are encoded
- A layer of plastic (polycarbonate).

How do CDs and DVDs work?

The light and its properties are also used in the field of optical storage, and lead to the technologies involved in CDs, DVDs, Blu-rays or physical supports for video games.

The concept behind is quite the same as the one used for the gramophone, only the way to read the record changes.

In both systems, the records are discs made of polymer or vinyl, **engraved** with the necessary data to recover the sound. The engraving runs in a spiral from the center to the exterior of the disc.

For the gramophone, the engraved signal corresponds exactly to the sound to be reproduced, the sapphire or diamond peak then read it and transmit it to a diaphragm or an amplifier to produce the sound.

In the case of the CD, how are the data stored?

To store data on a CD (sound, image, video), we convert these analog signals into digital signals. Digital signals are sequences of 1 and 0 (in binary). This information is "physically" represented by a succession of "pits" and "lands" on the surface of the CD. It is tempting to think that a pit is a "zero" and a land a "one" but the reality is somewhat different. Indeed all the pits and the lands are "zeros": it is the transition from low to high this information is encoded in sequence describing a wound coil from the center to the outside of the disc.

How are the data read?

To play your digital media, whether it is in our computer or in our DVD, a laser diode is used.

In the CD player a laser diode is used to read the media: the beam runs from the emitter to the surface of the CD, and is reflected. The returned beam interferes with the incident beam, and the interferences are observed thanks to a photodiode.

If the state of the surface is not modified (ie two following pits or lands), the received signal does not change and is interpreted as "0". In the contrary, if the surface shifts from land to pit or from pit to land then it is interpreted as "1".

Why has the DVD a larger storage capacity?

The discs have sizes that we cannot change. We must therefore find another way to store more data. The solution was found through the pits we have just seen.

Indeed, when the wavelength is smaller, the size of the points on the disc is also smaller. The size of the reading laser is the only reason for the best performance of DVD compared to CD. The CD uses a laser of 780nm while the DVD has a 630nm laser (20% reduction). This difference allows the storage of more information.

The DVDs and other optical media follow the same principle, since all video data or music can be sampled and digitized. The only difference is the Blu-Ray: as its name says, the laser beam used to read the media is blue and not red as in CD players.

Quiz for chapter 2

1- Which is the wavelength used for Blu-ray?

- a) 840nm
- b) 405nm
- c) 580nm

2- Which is the storage capacity of a DVD knowing that a CD has a capacity of 700MB?

- a) 4.7 GB
- b) 700 MB
- c) 25 GB

3- The pits of a Blu-Ray are:

- a) Deeper than those of a CD
- b) Shallower than those of a CD
- c) None of the above, they have exactly the same depth

Image & video

Photos invaded our universe; they help us to remember events of our lives. Our phones, our computers and cameras are capable of taking photos or videos. By what does it mean that these devices take pictures? What are the different sensors?

The camera allows to capture our daily scenes on Instagram or Snapchat. When we say "camera" we say "optical sensor". Today, digital cameras are supplied with only two types of sensors: a CMOS (Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor) or CCD (Charge Coupled Device).

The two chips are semiconductor materials, although their design and use is different as we shall see.

CCD sensor

A digital camera sensor is made of photovoltaic cells that measure the light intensity and color. This light intensity is then converted into electrical current. Each point of the sensor, which comprises a part of a pixel, records the light intensity to produce an image.

The CCD sensor is constituted by two superimposed components: the first is made of photosensitive cells, the second is the image pickup device. To restore color, each photosensitive cell has three filters: one red, one blue and one green, each filter being responsive to a single coordinate in order to pick up a color.

To reconstruct the image in the device, the charge transfer device transmits information to a collector which in turn transfers all charges to the converter. At the output of the converter, the information collected by the lens and the sensor is digital and can be processed by the circuits and processors of the digital camera and then stored in the memory of the binary format camera.

CMOS sensor

CMOS are composed of a **matrix of photodiodes** coupled with transistors (and electronics). Each point of the CMOS matrix (each pixel) corresponds to a point of the scene and it is possible to access the value of each pixel independently.

This type of sensor is similar to CCD, however CMOS works with one-step less because it's directly converting the load. Each photosite directly converts its load into a digital signal.

Thus, the CMOS sensor offers a faster acquisition and low power consumption compared to CCD and also is **cheaper** to produce.

Matrix images and vector graphics

There are generally two broad categories of images:

- Vector images: Vector images are representations of geometrical entities such as a circle, a rectangle or a segment. These are represented by mathematical formulas (a rectangle is defined by two points, a circle with a center and a radius, a curve by several points and an equation). This is the computer processor that will be responsible to "translate" these forms into information interpretable by the graphics card.
- Matrix images: The image data are represented by a two-dimensional array (matrix), each cell containing a pixel. The pixel (short for "picture element") represents the smallest component of a digital image.

Digital cameras and scanners use the matrix system. We will detail this system hereafter.

Matrix images

Pictures taken with a mobile phone or a digital camera are examples of matrix images.

Images Black & White

It is possible to represent this type of image by matrixes. For example, the small picture of Felix the Cat can be represented by a 35x35 matrix of size whose elements are 0 and 1. The item indicates the pixel color: 0 for a black pixel and 1 for a white pixel (a pixel is the smallest graphical element of a raster image, which can take only one color at a time). Digital images using only two colors are called binary images.

Greyscale Images

The greyscale image may also be represented by matrix. Each element determines the intensity of the corresponding pixel. For practical reasons, the majority of current digital database is using integers between 0 (for a black pixel, minimum color intensity) and 255 (for a white pixel, maximum intensity of color), which gives totally different shades of gray (this number is acceptable for websites images, for example).

Color images

Assuming that the eye has cones: receivers in Red, Green and enabling him to distinguish the different colors, in fact we can decompose the visible spectrum in terms of these three components. In summary our brain is able to recreate any color from these three primary colors Red, Green and Blue.

These three primary colors in additive synthesis are the basis of the RGB system used in video for display on the screens, and in imaging software. If you look at a color television screen with a magnifying glass, you'll see it appear in groups of three bright spots: one red, one green and one blue.

The combination of these three points gives a bright point (a pixel) of a certain color. The RGB system is one way of describing a computer in color. So the 255,255 triple {255} give white, {255, 0, 0} pure red, {100, 100, 100} gray, etc. The first number gives the red component, the second green component and the blue component last.

In the RGB system, the color image may be represented by three matrices. Each matrix determines the amount of red, green and blue which forms the image. The elements of these matrices are integers between 0 and 255 that determine the color intensity of the matrix for the corresponding pixel. Thus, with the RGB color model, it is possible to represent different colors. Some examples of RGB colors:

The characteristics of a matrix image

Each bitmap has technical characteristics: definition, resolution, depth.

Definition

The definition of a matrix image is the number of pixels in width and height (eg 800 X 600 pixels). Moreover when an image is more defined it consists of a large number of pixels, it is more "heavy",. It be possible, from digital cameras to express the definition in raw numbers: 3 million pixels for example, means 2048 x 1536 pixels image ratio 4/3, and 8 million pixels 3264 x 2448 pixels.

The resolution

Resolution is the number of pixels per display unit, usually the number of dots per inch, or DPI (dots per inch) (eg 300 dpi).

The depth

The depth or colour representation is the amount of information for each pixel. If we use 1 bit, each point of the image is a bit, the smallest unit of information on a hard drive: a 1 or a 0. If we use 8 bit or grey levels, each pixel is defined by one byte (8 bits) , giving 256 different grey levels.

An RGB image consists of three layers, the three additive colours Red Green and Blue. Three bytes, one for each colour (R, G, B) from which 256 X 256 X 256 colour possibilities, or 16,777,216 colours.

Reflex sensors and computer monitors

Sensors of cameras and displays use the same principle to save or create a colour, they mix the 3 primary colours:

- **R: Red**
- **G: Green**
- **B: Blue**

Basically, a screen is composed of pixels, each pixel includes three diodes (red, green and blue), by modulating the light intensity of each LED it can display any visible colour, it is called additive synthesis: it creates colour by mixing 3 diode lights.

The number of possible levels for each component is defined as the number of bits used to record the values:

- 8 bits allow 256 per component level or $256 \times 256 \times 256 = 16,000,000$ colours.
- 12 bits permit $4^9 = 262,144$ levels per component, over 60 billion of colours.

Summary

A digital image is an array of colored dots (pixels).

For example, a basic computer displays 1024 pixels in width and 768 pixels in height.

Color information of coding pixels:

- Black and white :
A single bit is sufficient to encode information, eg 0 for black and 1 for white.
- Greyscale image:
8 bits are used, giving 256 possible grayscale levels for the pixel, from 0 (black) to 255 (white).
- Color picture:
The color of each pixel is defined by three components: Red, Green and Blue. The intensity of each component is coded on 8 bits, so each component has a value between 0 (no color) to 255 (maximum color intensity). Thus the color of one pixel requires 24 bits (3 octets) to be coded.

The pixel color is obtained by additive synthesis, in particular:

- If the three components are 0: black,
- If the three components are the same: gray,
- If the three components are 255: white.

Quiz for chapter 3

- 1- A scientist in a research center is looking for a new camera sensor, which one will she choose?
 - a) A CMOS sensor
 - b) A CCD sensor
 - c) It doesn't matter
- 2- #441155 corresponds to
 - a) Deep blue
 - b) Red purple
 - c) Blue purple
- 3- Which one is the darkest of those grey hues?
 - a) #AAAAAA
 - b) #AFAFAF
 - c) #FAFAFA

Module 3: Photonics for Health & life

Microscopy

Lens magnification

Magnification is the process of **enlarging** something optically. For example, when you use a magnifying glass, you can observe an ant, which appears for example three times larger. Then we can say that the ant has been magnified.

The magnification (M) is the ratio of the image size to the object size, and it is also the ratio of the image distance to the object distance (see figure bellow)

$$y_2/y_1 = s_2/s_1 = M.$$

What type of lens is magnifying lens?

Convex lens is used as magnifying lens as they produce a highly magnified image of an object placed in their path (closer than the focal length). The magnification is seen in below figure that tells that if an object is placed on one side of a convex lens closer to it than the focal point, the image of the object is formed on the same side as the object which is highly magnified.

What is the concept of the optical microscope?

A microscope is an instrument used to produce enlarged images of small objects. The most common kind of microscope is an optical microscope, which uses lenses to form images from visible light.

An optical microscope with a single lens is known as a simple microscope. Simple microscopes include magnifying glasses and jeweller’s loupes. An optical microscope with two lenses is known as a compound microscope.

The basic parts of a compound microscope are the objective, which holds the lens near the specimen, and the eyepiece, which holds the lens near the observer.

The optical microscope [magnifies](#) an object in two steps (see figure below). In both steps optical systems acting like converging lenses are used:

1. The first step is to place the object between the single and double focal point. The result is a magnified, real image. This microscope lens (in reality an optical system consisting of several lenses) is called the objective.
2. Then a second lens is used to pick up this image exactly in its front focal point. As a result we generate a beam of parallel rays, but not a real image. This optical element is called eyepiece. The human eye is able to handle this parallel beam and generates an image onto its retina.

An optical microscope is mainly composed of the eyepiece and the different objectives. The objective is selected depending on the level of detail that shall be observed. The sample is placed on the table below the objective.

Finally, the illumination is an important part of a microscope. If it is not well regulated, the observation of the object is deteriorated: some details will not be observable.

What is the fluorescence microscope?

We have seen that the microscope allows us to study small objects. However, the quality of observation can be improved especially with the fluorescence microscope.

Fluorescence is the process realised by a **substance absorbing light with one wavelength (blue, violet) and re-emitting light with a different wavelength (green, yellow, red)**. Fluorescence microscopes use this phenomenon to generate images. The specimen is illuminated with a specific wavelength that is absorbed. It then emits light at a different wavelength, which is retrieved using filters.

In the following picture, we can see an example of a result using this technology:

Observation with Fluorescence Microscope

Quiz:

1- Where is the object placed that is to be observed?

- a) Arm
- b) On the objective
- c) Use technical terms from Fig. 5

2- To which system is the microscope similar?

- a) A telescope
- b) A magnifying glass
- c) Human vision

Imaging

Every day, our sight is helpful. Since our birth, it changes and every year an eye examination is recommended. How do eyes work? Why some people don't have good sight? What are the similarities with the camera?

What are the concepts of vision?

Diagram of the human eye

The human eye is made up of cornea, crystalline lens, retina and aqueous fluids. Each one plays an important role in vision. The cornea and the lens focus the image on the retina. The lens is essential since it is deformable and can perform the adjustment of the eye when the object is closer or further away, this is what we call accommodation.

The iris is the coloured part of the eye, it expands or not as required. It allows you to increase or decrease the brightness at the bottom of our eye.

All the passing light is going to the bottom of the eye, to the retina. The photoreceptor cells of the retina changes the light energy into electrical energy. This electrical signal is then transferred to the brain via the optic nerve. The information processing then takes place in the brain.

In the human eye, there are cone cells in the retina, which enable us to see different colours. In fact there are three types of cells. Each of them detects one colour: green, red and blue; and the combination of these colours creates the observed colour. Moreover, there are animals such as mantis shrimp, which have more type of cone cells and can also see different colours.

What are eye defects?

Vision is a clear mechanism, some people can't see without glasses due to an eye defect. The latter are due to the fact that the image is not focused on the retina.

There are several types of optical defects: myopia, hyperopia, astigmatism and presbyopia.

Myopia is the consequence of a too long eyeball; the image is focused before the retina. Thus a myopic has a very poor distance vision.

On the other hand, the hyperopia is too short eyeball; the image comes up behind the retina. Thus, the vision is blurred for near objects.

The astigmatic has blurred vision in some directions since its eyeball is deformed. Finally Presbyopia is the loss of elasticity of the lens; it is one of the consequences of old age.

The astigmatic has blurred vision in directions because of its deformed eyeball. Finally Presbyopia is the loss of elasticity of the lens, it is one of the consequences of old age.

To correct these defects **ophthalmologists usually prescribe optical lenses** in order to project the picture exactly onto the retina.

Finally, some people are **colour-blind**. The following picture can be used to determine if someone is affected by this defect. If the number seems unreadable, the answer is yes.

Test for colour blindness

What is the concept of the camera?

We have seen that the received images exist in our brain through a mechanism present in the eye. This system was useful for scientific inventions, since it has been imitated for creating cameras.

A **camera works like an eye**: the different elements of the eye and the camera can be matched. Indeed, each main element of a camera has its counterpart in the eye

Lens

Both the camera and the human eye have a lens that focuses light into an inverted image. One major difference between the two lenses, though, is that while a camera lens moves closer or farther from an object in order to bring it into focus, the lens of the human eye stay stationary. To bring an object into focus, muscles in the eye respond to instructions from the brain and change the shape of the lens, thus sharpening the image.

Retina (Film or Sensor)

Additionally, the eye's retina is like a camera's film or sensor onto which light is cast. In the eye, light passes through the lens and hits the retina, where rods and cones help transform the received image into electric impulses that are sent along the optic nerve to the brain. While both the retina and a camera's film or sensor are all highly sensitive to light, the eye is much more so, and performs much better in the dark -- even without a flash.

Iris (Aperture)

To allow the right amount of light, both the eye and a camera have an aperture. The eye's version is its iris working together with the pupil, which, just like a camera aperture, widens or narrows depending on the amount of ambient light. Therefore, just the right amount of light hits either the eye's retina or camera's film or sensor so as to present a clear, discernible image.

How do image CCD sensors work?

To create a camera, scientists have created a sensor similar to the human sensor named "Retina". This invention is the CCD, it is the simpler to manufacture and exists since 1970.

Fundamentally, a charge coupled device (CCD) is an integrated circuit etched onto a silicon surface forming light sensitive elements called pixels. They convert the received amount of light into a corresponding number of electrons. The stronger the light, the more electrons are generated. The electrons are converted into voltage and then transformed into numbers by means of an analogue-digital converter. The signal constituted by the numbers is processed by electronic circuits inside the camera.

CCD sensors register the amount of light from bright to dark with no colour information. We can talk about CCD image sensors "colour blind". To implement a colour in the camera, we place a filter called a "colour filter array" (CFA) in front of the sensor to allow the capture of primary colours. The most common colour registration method is RGB (Red, Green, and Blue). Red, green, and blue are the primary colours that, mixed in different combinations, can produce most of the colours visible to the human eye.

The most widespread and successful CFA has been the [Bayer pattern](#), which uses alternating rows of red-green and green-blue filters:

Quiz:

- 1- What is the consequence of a too short eyeball?
 - a) Myopia
 - b) Hyperopia
 - c) Astigmatism

- 2- What component of the eye may be associated to the objective of a camera?
 - a) The retina
 - b) Lens and cornea
 - c) The iris

3. Where must the image be positioned to achieve good vision?
 - a) On the lens
 - b) On the cornea
 - c) On the retina

Laser therapy

Lasers have emerged in the 1960s. They are used in all fields such as industry, physics and also medicine. How does such a light source help surgeons today? What are the effects of the laser on humans?

What are the biological interactions related to laser?

You all know lasers, you have already used them in physics experiments at school. However, you probably do not know laser effects on our bodies when we use them in the medical field.

Biological interactions between laser light and tissue depend on its wavelength, power and time of exposure to the laser beam. Several effects are possible such as electromechanical, photo-ablative, thermal or photochemical effect.

Also, laser radiation delivered via a fibre for photodynamic therapy can treat cancer.

Figure: Laser Medicine

What are the electromechanical effects?

When people decide to remove their tattoos, they pass through a laser procedure. This erases the tattoo.

This is the electromechanical effect that occurs when very strong and short laser pulses are applied on the tissue. This irradiance results in the creation of strong electric fields. The tissue then undergoes rupture and plasma formation is observed.

What are the photo-ablative effects?

You've already met people who have had surgery to remove their eye defects. These people with myopia or hyperopia were treated with laser light to change the curvature of their cornea. Ophthalmic laser are used because of their precision and to avoid contact with the tissue.

This method is used in the medical field, to automate the operations. This is called the photo ablative effect. These photons have higher energies than the energy that keeps the molecules intact. Thus, the molecular bonds break during the laser exposure. Hence a breakdown of tissues is obtained.

What are the thermal effects?

In medicine, it's sometimes important to coagulate the blood of patients to save their life. For this, it is possible to use the laser to induce thermal effects.

This effect is largely used today. This is a three-stage process: a light-heat conversion, a transfer of heat in the skin, and tissue reaction to the temperature.

This effect may cause hyperthermia (increased temperature), volatilization and bleeding of the tissues (necrosis). It is widely used in medicine: ophthalmology, surgery or dermatology for treating skin lesions.

What are the photochemical effects?

Cancer is very complex to treat. To assist in the elimination of cancer cells in a localized area of your body, you need an effective method which might include photochemical effects caused by laser light.

In medicine, photochemical effects are used in two steps:

- Application of a photosensitizer in the lesion to be treated
- Illumination of this lesion with low intensity light

This promotes chemical reactions in the tissues which kill cancer cells

Quiz:

1 - What effect is used to change ophthalmic defects?

- a) The photochemical effect
- b) The electromechanical effect
- c) The photoablative effect

Spectroscopy

Stars and illuminated planets are out of reach for a hands-on study. The same is true for certain chemicals which are present in very small quantities, toxic or radioactive.

Luckily, many of these objects interact with light in a way that we can get information on them by examining that light.

Spectroscopy is the science of studying the ‘spectral composition’ of light (simply put: the various colours which are present) coming from objects like the sun, the moon or an unknown chemical. This is done by use of so-called spectrometer, see Figure below.

What is a spectrophotometer?

Figure: Spectrophotometer

In this figure below you see a spectrometer for examining a sample container with an unknown chemical. The principle is simple: You choose light of one wavelength (colour), shine it onto the sample and see how much light passes through or get scattered. Then, you take the next wavelength and do the same. After doing this for a number of wavelengths you’ll compare the data you got to a database which contains transmission- and scattering data on all kinds of chemical groups. If you find a match in the database you’ll know what’s in your sample container.

In practice, a spectroscope performs those tedious measurements automatically. You have 1 or 2 light sources which generate a beam in the right wavelength range; from there you use filters and a monochromator to select a single wavelength. Then, you split up the beam. One part will go through your unknown sample, the other one through a ‘reference’ sample, which is necessary to get precise results. Photodiodes behind your sample container and the reference each measure the transmitted light intensity. A computer collects the data for each wavelengths, draws a graph and compares it to its database.

What is the theory of spectroscopy in the IR (infra-red) domain?

We have seen how a basic spectroscope works, but there is another spectroscope which works with infrared light.

The IR spectroscopy uses the same mounting as a spectrophotometer but illuminates the sample with a **large IR spectrum**. As atoms and molecules possess specific resonance frequencies where they absorb best, knowing which IR frequencies have been absorbed typical chemical groups can be spotted.

For example, the OH group, characterizing alcohols and water matches with absorption near 3650-3590 cm^{-1} .

Major Functional Group	Absorption Frequency Region			
O-H	3650-3590			
N-H	3500-3300	1650-1590	900-650	
=CH-H	3100-3070	1420-1410	900-880	
=C-H	3100-3000	2000-1600		
C-H	2900-2700	1440-1320		
=-CH ₃	2880-2860	2970-2950	1380-1370	1470-1430
O-H	2700-2500	1320-1210	950-900	
C≡C	2140-2100			
C=O	1750-1700			
C=C	1600-1500			
C-N	1340-1250			
C-O-C	1200-1180			
-C-H	770-730			

Figure : IR spectroscopy handbook

Quiz:

1- Which radiations are absorbed by a transparent solution?

- a) White light
- b) None
- c) IR or UV radiation

2- Which is the radiation most absorbed by a red solution?

- a) red light
- b) yellow light
- c) green light

Module 4: Photonics for Energy, lighting & display keywords

Lighting

Semiconductors

The creation of the first incandescent light bulb by Thomas Edison allowed many technologies to be developed such as electrical lamps. However its size cannot be reduced a lot, to create much more effective and smaller devices, a new technology was needed.

Starting in the 30's, materials known as **semiconductors** were more and more studied because of their interesting properties.

All atoms are composed of a nucleus, made of protons and neutrons, and a cloud of **electrons** organized in bands of different levels of energy but in the case of semiconductors their structure (see figure 1) allows either to absorb or emit photons. Indeed non-excited electrons in the **Valence Band** can go to the Conduction Band when given energy that is to say when absorbing a photon. It creates a positive **hole** in the Valence Band. At the opposite excited electrons in the **Conduction Band** can go to the Valence Band by emitting a photon and fill the hole.

Figure 1: structure of a semiconductor

Semiconductors generally have a crystalline architecture and the most used is silicon. That is the material used to create a disc containing peace messages from many countries and left on the moon in 1969.

Junction diode

Knowing these properties, physicists mixed semiconductors with other materials in small quantity to increase the mobility of the electrons. Introducing impurities in semiconductors is called **doping** and it is divided in two categories: **N and P type**.

The energy difference between Valence and Conduction bands is called **band gap** and defines the level of energy needed to emit or absorb photons: the higher it is the more energy the photon needs to have to be absorbed.

N type materials bring more electrons and artificially decrease the level of energy of the Conduction band and so the band gap.

Figure 2: N type effect

P type materials steal the electrons of the semiconductor and create holes in the Valence band of the semiconductor. They artificially increase the level of energy of the band and so decrease the band gap.

Figure 3: P type effect

These 2 types of doping are often combined to create a **PN junction**. The border between P and N types is a particular area where electrons and holes flow to the opposite band creating a nearly non-conductive area. This property can be changed with the voltage of the junction. For instance a **junction diode** is a PN junction where the current can flow in one direction (forward voltage) but not in the other (reverse voltage).

Nowadays PN junction are basic components of most of integrated circuits, transistors and Light-Emitting Diode (LED) that use little electricity, are small and cheap light sources. In addition new PN junctions made of organics materials are now used to create Organic LED (OLED), Organic Photodiode (OPD) or Organic Photovoltaics (OPV). These components have nearly the same efficiency and cost than silicon but their production creates less carbon dioxide, and organic materials pollute less than silicon.

Quiz for chapter 1

To emit light, semiconductors must absorb:

1. electrons
2. photons
3. holes

A big band gap makes:

1. efficient semiconductors
2. inefficient semiconductors
3. nothing

Compared to silicon, organic materials are: `

1. more efficient and pollutant
2. less efficient and cleaner
3. pollutant but cheaper

Energy

Photovoltaic effect

As seen in the “Lighting” chapter, electrons of semiconductors move when it is enlightened and holes are created. The **moving electrons** create a current of electricity. It is called **photovoltaic effect**. The current can be improved when using doped semiconductors and creating a PN junction to increase the number of electrons moving.

The choice of the semiconductor to be used is very important due to its role in the final product characteristics:

- Materials sensible to low light are used to make photodiodes (see module 5);
- Materials with less sensibility but bigger electricity current compose **solar panel**.

Solar panels are a very interesting technology to replace nuclear plants but also make possible the use of electrical devices in isolated places such as in space. For example Philae, the robot which landed on comet Churyumov in November 2014 has batteries running thanks to solar panels.

Display

Pixels

All cameras or image creator devices have the same basic component: an **array of pixels**. A pixel is an area of semiconductor that detects light emitted by the object seen by the camera. An electric circuit receives the information from all the pixels and assembles it to make the image.

Figure 5: Pixel array operation

The figure 5 shows that **enlightened pixels** appear white on the screen whereas **unlit pixels** are black. In a real sensor the color on the screen depends of the intensity created by the pixel. For instance black and white images can have more than 65235 shades of grey.

The size of the pixel is important too. An object cannot be seen if it is smaller than the pixel.

Figure 6: 2 different sizes of pixel

As seen on figure 6, pixels will not detect smaller objects because light can still reach the pixels so they appear white on the screen. At the opposite if the object is bigger than the pixel no light reach's the pixel and it appears black on the screen. The size of a pixel is called **resolution**.

LCD screen

We have seen that pixels can be used to “capture” an image but they also are used to create an image on screens of computer, smartphones... Nowadays most of the screens are Liquid Crystal Display (**LCD**) screens. These screens are made of pixels composed of multiple layers:

Figure 7: layers of a LCD screen pixel

As said in Module 1 light has an electric field with a particular direction. **Polarizers** are filters that let pass only some of those directions. In the figure, the crossed polarizers let no light come through. However when changing the voltage of the liquid crystal with the transparent electrodes it changes its physical properties: it becomes a polarizer. This way some light might go through the pixel. Modifying the voltage change the direction of polarization of the crystals and so the amount of light the user can see. It allows to get black and white images.

To obtain **colored images** red, blue and green filters must be added to **groups of 3 pixels**.

Figure 8: layers of a LCD screen color pixel

LCD screens are thin and allow the creation of small devices like smartphones. It is an omnipresent technology but it is surprising to think that the first sales started in the early 2000s in most of the countries.

Module 5: Photonics for Security, metrology & sensors

Metrology & sensors

Sensors

Automatic or security systems must be able to “see” their surroundings. This need leads to the creation of sensors. A sensor is a device able to **detect a change** of a parameter in a situation. Depending on the situation, many parameters can be considered and different sensors can be used. Photonics allows to detect lots of different parameters.

Chemical reaction can create **change of color**. For instance the pH of a solution can be measured with pH-paper which color changes depending of the pH. It can help determining the quality of a solution.

The current delivered by a resistance changes with the temperature so a measure of current can be used to deduce the temperature. For instance **thermic cameras** are made of very small resistances that are used as pixels and the image formed shows the different temperatures.

Figure 9: Human seen with a thermic camera

Thermic cameras can be used for Health applications, building isolation or security (prevent fire or explosions).

Other materials can detect the change of strength of a **pressure**. They may be used for example as an on/off button or placed in a newly made wall to make sure it does not move.

Finally **Photodiodes** are often used as **displacement or position** sensor. They detect changes of light and the place where there is less light is normally where the person is localized. For instance automatic lamps emit IR light which is not visible for a human eye and measure the reflection. When the reflection changes the visible light is activated because a human is walking near the lamp.

Security & safety

Food inspection

Safety regulations in quality controls or security applications require **fast and accurate sensors** to get reliable results.

Food inspection must determine if foodstuff are eatable, toxic, rotten... the most common test is to take samples, dilute them in water and place drops in a petri box to **observe** the development of **bacteria**. Depending on the kind of bacteria created and their size, biologists can deduce the quality of the food. However it takes too long for a biologist to check himself all the samples and count the clusters of bacteria so an automatic detection device is needed. The first possible solution is to use a camera:

Figure 10: detection of bacteria with camera

Light goes through the empty space but bacteria reflect or absorb it so the camera will see black spots where the clusters are. A software then detects, measures and counts the clusters. This method is fast and efficient but this kind of detection often requires to be thin and endowed with a large field of view which is difficult with a camera (it needs at least a few centimeters of thickness to see the whole box). In addition the cost can be high.

Another method is to place the bacteria in water:

Figure 11: Water analyzer

Light is injected in the water and photodiodes measure reflected and transmitted light. The measures give optical properties of the bacteria and biologists easily deduce the kind of bacteria this is. A similar method is to add a polarizer to measure the optical rotation i.e. the turning angle of matter to get linear polarized light. The water analysis method is potentially cheaper than using cameras but it is hard to distinguish different bacteria.

Thanks to these methods of detection and the new knowledge about diseases, the number of food poisoning has drastically been dropping over the past century.

Air quality surveillance

Pollution is one of the most important problem of our century for it causes great damages to the environment and can also harm people. **Air quality control** is needed to prevent major problems or epidemics. All over the world, samples of air are taken and tested to detect and measure the quantity of molecules such as carbon monoxide, ozone or sulfur dioxide. Photonics provides some detection systems:

Figure 12: air quality control

Air sample are enlightened with Infrared (IR) or Ultraviolet (UV) light and transmitted light is measured to determine the absorption of the sample.

- Carbon monoxide quantity is determined with the IR absorption;
- Ozone quantity is determined with the UV absorption;
- Sulfur dioxide emits visible light when enlightened with UV so measure of visible light gives information about the quantity of sulfur dioxide.

Another test often made is the luminol test: nitrogen oxide reacts with luminol and it creates light that is detected by the photodiode.

Figure 13: Chemiluminescent reaction

Biometrics

Digital codes are not trusty security systems for hackers can easily find or crack them. As a consequence new secure ways of **personal identification** are required. Human body information can be used for all bodies are different and some data are hard to fake. Those information are called **biometrics**.

Fingerprints are the most known biometrics and the oldest. It has been used by the police for more than hundred years. At first ink was used and policemen compared themselves the fingerprints of suspects. The quality was poor and it took lots of time to identity one. Now ink can be used but most of fingerprints images (like in a passport) are made with cameras:

Figure 14: Fingerprint detection

Finger placed on a glass panel and light reflects on fingerprints to go the camera that gives a clean image if the resolution is high enough.

Figure 15: image of a fingerprint

Fingerprints are easy to read and systems can be integrated in small devices but it is too well-known and people put fingerprints everywhere so criminals can find them and they have ways to fake fingerprints. In addition a sensor where everybody places their fingers is not hygienic. That's why other biometrics were studied.

Eyes also have interesting patterns that can be used for identification.

The first one is the **pattern of the iris**:

Figure 16: iris pattern from "Iris recognition", Dr J.Daughman

Figure 17: Iris pattern recognition

Figure 16 shows the kind of pattern sought. On figure 17 we see that the devices send light to the eye and image the reflected light. The image is processed on computer to extract the pattern and compare it to the data bank.

It is also possible to do a **retinal scan** to get the pattern created by the veins:

Figure 18: Retinal scan

Operation is basically the same as iris recognition but IR light is used to go through the eye and reflect on the veins. The **vein pattern** image is processed to be extracted and then compared to the data bank.

Both techniques are normally touchless and fast but they require the subject neither to move nor to blink. In addition heavy image processing is needed. These techniques are fine for fixed devices but portable devices have to be light and have low power consumption.

Last possibility is to observe **vein pattern from fingers**. Indeed it has been proved that even homozygote twins have different patterns so it can be used as biometrics. This method is recent and only few devices have been created yet. Two general designs are possible:

Figure 19: Finger veins detection

Both designs use IR light that go through (only 40% of reflection) flesh and bones but is absorbed and reflected by veins. As a consequence veins appear darker than flesh on the image. The reflection design is useful to get thin devices but transmission design can also be used even if more light is needed for the transmission of finger is very low (less than 10%). The image is then processed and compared to a data bank. The texture and color of skin has to be considered too because optical properties might change depending on the person using the device.

It is a new biometrics and it requires more studies to be used. For example the texture and color of skin has to be considered too because optical properties might change depending on the person using the device. Still it is a non-invasive method of identification and much easier and comfortable to apply than eye reading.

Quiz

The detection of different objects with light is possible because:

1. they don't have the same optical properties
2. they don't have the same size
3. one is closer to the sensor

IR light can be used to detect:

1. fingerprints
2. iris pattern
3. veins

When the number of bacteria in a water analyzer increases:

1. light transmitted increases
2. light transmitted decreases
3. it changes nothing

